

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF MINI TRACTOR DRAWN COMBINE TILLAGE TOOL AND CULTIVATOR FOR SEED BED PREPARATION IN SANDY LOAM SOIL CONDITIONS

Dr.K.L.Dabhi¹, Anupama Sharma² Pratham Sen³ Anup Soni⁴ Shradhha Kaushik⁵

1. Assistant Professor, Department of Farm Machinery and Power Engineering, College of Agricultural Engineering and Technology, Anand Agricultural University, Godhra, Gujarat-INDIA kldabhi876@gmail.com
2. B.Tech.student, Department of Farm Machinery and Power Engineering, College of Agricultural Engineering and Technology, Anand Agricultural University, Godhra, Gujarat, India
3. B.Tech.student, Department of Farm Machinery and Power Engineering, College of Agricultural Engineering and Technology, Anand Agricultural University, Godhra, Gujarat, India
4. B.Tech.student, Department of Farm Machinery and Power Engineering, College of Agricultural Engineering and Technology, Anand Agricultural University, Godhra, Gujarat, India
5. B.Tech.student, Department of Farm Machinery and Power Engineering, College of Agricultural Engineering and Technology, Anand Agricultural University, Godhra, Gujarat, India
6. B.Tech.student, Department of Farm Machinery and Power Engineering, College of Agricultural Engineering and Technology, Anand Agricultural University, Godhra, Gujarat, India
7. B.Tech.student, Department of Farm Machinery and Power Engineering, College of Agricultural Engineering and Technology, Anand Agricultural University, Godhra, Gujarat, India

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Abstract

Mini tractor drawn combine tillage tool (CTT) and cultivator are widely used by the farmers for seed preparation. The CTT was developed by FMPE department of CAET, AAU, Godhra as a low-cost alternative to reduce the number of passes and time saving for seed bed preparation. The study compared the performance of CTT and cultivator in sandy loam soil with different gears and speeds. The data were analysed using design expert software version 13. The performance parameters measured were speed of operation, theoretical field capacity (TFC), effective field capacity (EFC), wheel slippage, field efficiency, draft requirement, unit draft requirement, power requirement, energy requirement, fuel consumption, soil volume moved (SVM), mean mass diameter (MMD) and cost of operation. The results showed that CTT had better performance than cultivator in most of the parameters, especially in TFC, EFC, energy requirement, fuel consumption, and cost of operation. The optimal operational parameters for CTT and cultivator were also determined by the software. The study concluded that mini tractor drawn CTT is a suitable implement for small and marginal farmers to prepare shallow depth seedbeds in sandy loam soil and save costs. The cost of operation of CTT was 36.98% lower than the cultivator.

Keywords: Effective field capacity, Mean mass diameter, Draft requirement, Energy requirement, Wheel slippage.

Introduction

The agricultural sector of India faces a huge challenge: how to feed its growing population, which is expected to reach 1.6 billion by 2050, from a limited cultivated area. To increase food production, the productivity of the land must be improved by increasing cropping intensity and reducing turn around time. Mandal (2017) studied that small and marginal farms are one of the immense challenges for farm mechanization in the West Bengal state of India. This requires more mechanization, which is currently low in India. The use of machines for agricultural production has been a remarkable development in Indian agriculture. The productivity level of agricultural commodities depends largely on the efficient utilization of available resources and the timeliness of agricultural operations.

Most Indian farmers use conventional tillage, which involves many passes over a field with various soil-turning and soil-pulverizing equipments, such as mould board plough, disk ploughs, spike-toothed harrows and so many. By the use of this type of tillage equipments is costly, consume a lot of fuel, and causes soil compaction. Moreover, many farmers do not match the tractor and the implement properly, resulting in under loading of the tractor engine and poor efficiency. These problems can be solved by either increasing the speed and width of the tillage implements or reducing the number of passes needed for tillage operations to prepare the seedbed without compromising the quality of work. However, the land sizes in India are small, which limits the possibility of increasing the speed or width of the existing implements. Therefore, a better solution may be to reduce the number of passes by combining two or more field operations with the use of combination tillage implements. Javadi and Hajiahmad (2006) conducted a study on effect of a new combined implement for reducing secondary tillage operation and the results indicated that combined machine improved some soil physical properties, which were important for secondary tillage such as clod breaking and surface uniformity. These implements can help in saving time, labour and fuel costs for seedbed preparation. The combination tillage implement consists of either active-passive or passive-passive tillage elements. Some studies have been conducted

in India on the development and performance evaluation of 2WD tractor drawn combination tillage implements. Therefore, a study was carried out to consider the importance of mini tractor drawn combined tillage tool for small and marginal farmers to ascertain the better one to achieve an essential level of seedbed preparation.

Materials And Methods**Experimental Design**

In the study the mini tractor drawn combined tillage tool and mini-tractor drawn cultivator were studied in field conditions. Each of the implement was tested as per number of treatments suggested by design expert software. Response Surface Method was used with Central Composite Design (CCD) with face centered and two blocks were used to determine the best operating parameters for the implement.

About Design Expert

File Version 13.0.5.0

Study Type -Response Surface

Subtype – Randomized

Design Type -Central Composite

Runs 14.00

Design Model Quadratic

Blocks 2.00

Build Time (Ms) 5.02

Experimental Site And Layout

Field experiment was conducted at College of Agricultural Engineering and Technology, Godhra in March 2023, District-Panchmahal, Gujarat.

Treatments

Each implement has been given the treatments as under:

i. Engine Speed: 1650 rpm, 1750 rpm, 1850 rpm

ii. Depth of operation: 10 cm, 12.5 cm, 15 cm

iii. Block 1: H1 (1st gear, high speed)

iv. Block 2: L3 (3rd gear, low speed)

Field layout for combined tillage operation

Plot size = 40 m × 3 m

For 14 treatments, total field area = 40 m × 3 m × 14 = 1680 m²**Table1: Speed of operation and depth of operation for combined tillage tool**

Plot No.	Engine Speed (RPM)	Depth (cm)	Tractor speed
1	1650	10.0	H1
2	1750	12.5	H1

3	1750	12.5	H1
4	1850	15.0	H1
5	1650	15.0	H1
6	1850	10.0	H1
7	1750	12.5	H1
8	1750	12.5	L3
9	1750	10.0	L3
10	1650	12.5	L3
11	1750	12.5	L3
12	1850	12.5	L3
13	1750	12.5	L3
14	1750	15.0	L3

Field layout for cultivator operation

Plot size = 40m × 3m for first tilling and 40m × 3m for cross tilling

Total field area = 40m × 3m × 14 = 1680 m² (for one pass operation), here first tilling was performed in one direction and then cross tilling was performed over first tilling in perpendicular direction of first tilling

Table 2: Speed of operation and depth of operation for combined cultivator

Plot No.	Engine Speed (RPM)	Depth (cm)	Tractor speed
1	1650	10.00	H1
2	1750	12.50	H1
3	1750	12.50	H1
4	1850	15.00	H1
5	1650	15.00	H1
6	1850	10.00	H1
7	1750	12.50	H1
8	1750	12.50	L3
9	1750	10.00	L3
10	1650	12.50	L3
11	1750	12.50	L3
12	1850	12.50	L3
13	1750	12.50	L3
14	1750	15.00	L3

Soil moisture content and bulk density of experimental plot were determined by standard method.

Field Capacity : Field capacity is the capacity of the implement to cover area in per unit time.

Theoretical field capacity: Theoretical field capacity of machine is the rate of field coverage that would be obtained if the machine was performing its function at 100% of the time at the rated speed and always covered 100% of its rated width.

$$\text{Theoretical field capacity (ha/h)} = \frac{\text{Rated width of machine, m} \times \text{speed of travel, km/h}}{10}$$

Effective field capacity: The Effective field capacity is the actual rate of coverage by the machine, based upon the total field time. The machine was operated with a fixed speed for continuous field work for a fixed time the area covered during the period was measured to determine the average output per hour. **Effective field capacity (ha/h)** = $\frac{\text{Actual area covered, ha}}{\text{Time required to cover field, h}}$

Field Efficiency

The term field efficiency is used to describe the efficiency of the machine in operation. It is the ratio of effective field capacity to the theoretical field capacity and expressed in percentage.

$$\text{Field efficiency (\%)} = \frac{\text{Effective field capacity}}{\text{Theoretical field capacity}} \times 100$$

Fig.1 Field performance with combine tillage tool

Fig.2 Field performance with cultivator

Wheel Slippage

The measurement of wheel slip was based on the fixed number of rear wheel revolutions. The distance covered in ten-wheel revolutions was recorded with and without load and the values were used to calculate slip using the following expression:

$$\text{Wheel slippage (\%)} = \frac{M_2 - M_1}{M_2} \times 100$$

Where,

M₂ = Distance covered in 10 revolutions of the tractor drive wheel at no load, (m)

M_1 = Distance covered in 10 revolutions of tractor drive wheel with load (m).

Draft requirement of the implements

Draft was measured using a digital drawbar dynamometer of capacity 1000 kg, attached to the front of the tractor on which the implement was mounted. Another auxiliary tractor was used to pull the

implement mounted tractor through the drawbar dynamometer. The auxiliary tractor pulls the implement-mounted tractor with the latter in neutral gear but with the implement in the operating position. The difference between the two readings (onload and offload), gives the draft of the implement

Fig.3 Draft measurement of CTT in the field

Unit Draft

$$\text{Unit draft (kgf/cm}^2\text{)} = \frac{\text{Draft}}{\text{Cross-sectional area of furrow}}$$

Power Requirement: Power requirement of different implements were calculated with the following formula-

$$\text{Power requirement (hp)} = \frac{\text{Draft(kgf)} \times \text{speed(m/s)}}{75}$$

Energy Requirement: The energy requirement of different treatments was calculated on the following basis.

E= P/A

Where,

E = Energy requirement, hp-h/ha

P= Power requirement, hp

A= Actual field capacity, ha/h

Fuel consumption: The tractor’s fuel supply was cut off and replaced by an auxiliary cylinder and the excess fuel from the injector system was collected in the same cylinder. The cylinder was filled before and after each treatment, and the difference was recorded as the fuel consumed.

Soil volume disturbed: Soil volume disturb is the measure of amount of soil volume disturbed from the original position in unit period of time

V =10000SD

Where,

V = Soil volume disturbed (m³ /h),

S = Effective field capacity (ha/h)

D = Depth of cut (m)

Soil Pulverization: Soil pulverization is the process of breaking of soil into small aggregates resulting from the action of tillage forces. The mean mass diameter (MMD) of the soil aggregates is considered as index of soil pulverization and can be determined by the sieve analysis of the soil sample through a set of standard test sieves (IS: 460-1962).

$$\text{MMD} = \frac{1}{W} \times (A+2.4B+3.4C+4.6D+6.8E+9.6F+XG)$$

Where,

MMD = Mean Mass Diameter

W= A+B+C+D+E+F+G

X= Mean of measured dia. of soil clods retained on the largest sieve

G= Amount of particles greater than 11.2mm

Cost analysis: The operating cost of the combine tillage tool and cultivator was determined by straight line method by considering 10 percent depreciation of tractor and implements per year.

Optimization of tillage operation

Optimization of tillage operations for both the implements was also carried out using the design expert software by concentrating on different factors as suggested by the software. The optimization is done for depth of operation response, EFC and, cost of operation response. The best result was obtained by keeping the cost of operation as minimum, EFC as maximum, depth of operation as maximum and all other parameters in range in optimization feature of Design Expert.

Results And Discussion

The performance evaluation of the treatments on mini tractor drawn combined tillage tool and comparison of its performance with the mini tractor drawn cultivator implement in terms of speed of operation, wheel slippage, field capacity, field efficiency, fuel consumption, draft, unit draft, power requirements, energy requirement and soil volume disturbance

Soil moisture content: The soil moisture content of the field was measured in the depth range of 0-15 cm and the result revealed that the average moisture content was **13.94 %**.Moisture content for soil is computed on dry basis (Tayel et al. (2015)) concluded that fuel consumption and wheel slippage of tillage operation is greatly affected by soil moisture, tractor speed and the working depth.

Bulk density: The mean data on bulk density before tillage operations at 0 - 15 cm depth was recorded in the range of 1.22 g/cm³ to 1.25 g/cm³ with the average value of 1.24 g/cm³

Table 3: Optimization table for mini tractor drawn CTT

Number	Engine	Depth of operation	Speed of operation	TFC	EFC	Field capacity	Net draft	Unit draft	Draft per ha	Power	Wheel slip	Fuel consumption	Fuel consumption (l/ha)	Cost of operation	Costs of operation	soil volume manipulate	Energy	MMD	Desirabilit	Sele
1.00	185	15.00	4.39	0.66	0.51	82.7	231.	0.10	154.	3.74	8.41	1.87	3.49	410.63	795.07	759.44	6.82	11.9	0.73	
2.00	184	15.00	4.38	0.66	0.51	82.7	231.	0.10	154.	3.72	8.40	1.86	3.49	409.69	795.07	758.60	6.82	11.9	0.73	

6.00	165	185	14.4	2.91	0.44	0.38	87.2	223.	0.10	148.	2.36	6.89	1.06	2.70	305.	795.	533.	6.23	11.8	0.49
5.00	185	185	14.0	4.51	0.68	0.53	82.3	228.	0.11	152.	3.79	8.24	1.88	3.48	412.	795.	722.	6.78	11.9	0.70
4.00	185	185	14.7	4.42	0.66	0.52	82.6	230.	0.10	153.	3.75	8.36	1.87	3.49	410.	795.	750.	6.81	11.9	0.73
3.00	185	185	14.8	4.41	0.66	0.52	82.6	230.	0.10	153.	3.74	8.38	1.87	3.49	410.	795.	753.	6.82	11.9	0.73

The best result was obtained at 1850 rpm for 15.0 cm depth, at which speed of operation was obtained as 4.39 km/h, and value for TFC is 0.65 ha/h, value for EFC value is 0.51 ha/h, field efficiency was obtained as 82.74%, Net draft was obtained as 231.33 kgf, Unit draft valued 0.1 kg/cm², Power consumed was 3.73 hp with a wheel slippage of 8.4%, Fuel consumption per hectare was 3.49 l/ha, Fuel consumption per hour was 1.86 l/h, Energy requirement was 6.821 hp-h/ha. Soil volume disturbed was 759.437 m³. Cost of operation was Rs. 795.06 per hectare. Hence, it gets a desirability value of 0.732 among other speeds.

Table 4: Optimization table for mini tractor drawn cultivator

Number	Engine Speed	Depth of operation	Speed of Operation	TFC	EFC	Field efficiency	Net draft	Unit draft	Draft per unit length	Power	Wheel slip	Fuel consumption(l/h)	Fuel consumption/l/ha	volume manipulated	Energy req	cost of operation	MMD	Desirability
1	1850	14.441	4.894	0.367	0.305	84.366	223.362	0.103	148.955	3.932	8.852	1.634	5.454	1762.66	12.72	1261.74	13.397	0.711
2	1850	14.418	4.897	0.368	0.305	84.381	223.193	0.103	148.843	3.929	8.843	1.633	5.448	1761.14	12.71	1260.34	13.396	0.711
3	1850	14.461	4.891	0.367	0.305	84.353	223.504	0.103	149.05	3.934	8.86	1.634	5.458	1763.93	12.728	1262.91	13.398	0.711
4	1850	14.399	4.899	0.368	0.305	84.392	223.062	0.103	148.756	3.928	8.836	1.633	5.444	1759.96	12.703	1259.27	13.395	0.711
5	1850	14.479	4.889	0.367	0.304	84.342	223.629	0.103	149.134	3.936	8.866	1.634	5.462	1765.05	12.735	1263.97	13.398	0.711
6	1850	14.5	4.886	0.367	0.304	84.329	223.776	0.103	149.232	3.938	8.874	1.634	5.467	1766.35	12.744	1265.19	13.399	0.711

The best result was obtained at 1850 rpm for 14.44 cm depth, at which speed of operation was obtained as 4.89 km/h, and value for TFC is 0.36 ha/h and EFC value is 0.30 ha/h, field efficiency was obtained as 84.36%, Net draft was obtained as 223.34 kgf, Unit draft valued 0.10 kg/cm², Power consumed was 3.93 hp with a wheel slippage of 8.85%, Fuel consumption per hectare was 5.54 l/ha. Fuel consumption per unit hour was 1.63 l/h. Energy requirement was 12.71 hp-h/ha. Soil volume disturbed was 1762.54 m³. Cost of operation was Rs. 1261.63 per hectare. Hence, it gets a desirability value of 0.711 among other speeds.

Conclusion:

Mini tractor is found very useful and economical mechanized power for various farm operations for small and marginal farmers. Design expert (version 13) was used to evaluate the results of performance of the combined tillage tool and the cultivator at various treatments for different engine speed (1650, 1750, 1850) rpm and various depth of operation (10, 12.5, 15) cm. Various gear settings for the mini tractor were tested for operation of the combined tillage tool and the cultivator but high speed H1 (1st gear, high speed) and L3 (3rd gear, low speed) speed and gear position performed satisfactory. With the help of design expert software various engineering parameters were analyzed as well as optimized to determine the better implement for shallow depth seedbed preparation.

The result of the study revealed the following conclusions:

The TFC and EFC were higher for the CTT than the cultivator by 0.3 ha/h, 0.205 ha/h respectively, and both increased with engine speed and decreased with depth of operation.

The field efficiency was slightly higher for the cultivator than the CTT on an average 1.616 % . The draft, unit draft, power, and energy requirement were similar for both the CTT and the cultivator, and depended on the speed and depth of operation.

The fuel consumption were lower for the CTT than the cultivator by on an average 1.964 l/ha in all cases and higher by 0.236 l/h.

The SVM and MMD were higher for the cultivator than the CTT in all cases, and varied with engine speed and depth of operation.

The best results for both the CTT and the cultivator were obtained at 1850 rpm, with slightly different depths of operation.

The CTT had higher TFC, EFC than the cultivator, but lower energy requirement

In case of CTT soil volume disturbed was higher by 1003.12 m³ and cost of operation by 466.67 Rs/ha .

The CTT is recommended for small and marginal farmers due to its lower fuel and cost per hectare.

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Table 5. Variation in performance of some important parameters with respect to depth of operation and engine speed

	Mini tractor drawn CTT	Mini tractor drawn cultivator
FIELD EFFICIENCY	<p>Factor Coding: Actual</p> <p>3D Surface</p> <p>Field efficiency (%)</p> <p>Design Points:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Above Surface ○ Below Surface <p>76.73 89.05</p> <p>X1 = A X2 = B</p>	<p>Factor Coding: Actual</p> <p>3D Surface</p> <p>Field efficiency (%)</p> <p>Design Points:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Above Surface ○ Below Surface <p>82.03 93.29</p> <p>X1 = A X2 = B</p>
NET DRAFT	<p>Factor Coding: Actual</p> <p>3D Surface</p> <p>Net draft (kgf)</p> <p>Design Points:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Above Surface ○ Below Surface <p>199.00 235.00</p> <p>X1 = A X2 = B</p>	<p>Factor Coding: Actual</p> <p>3D Surface</p> <p>Net draft (kgf)</p> <p>Design Points:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Above Surface ○ Below Surface <p>175.00 236.00</p> <p>X1 = A X2 = B</p>
SOIL VOLUME MANIPULATED	<p>Factor Coding: Actual</p> <p>3D Surface</p> <p>soil volume manipulated (m3/h)</p> <p>Design Points:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Above Surface ○ Below Surface <p>372.41 942.51</p> <p>X1 = A X2 = B</p>	<p>Factor Coding: Actual</p> <p>3D Surface</p> <p>volume manipulated (m3/h)</p> <p>Design Points:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Above Surface ○ Below Surface <p>817.36 1956.52</p> <p>X1 = A X2 = B</p>
COST OF OPERATION	<p>Factor Coding: Actual</p> <p>3D Surface</p> <p>Costs of operation (Rs/ha)</p> <p>Design Points:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Above Surface ○ Below Surface <p>636.48 1039.46</p> <p>X1 = A X2 = B</p>	<p>Factor Coding: Actual</p> <p>3D Surface</p> <p>cost of operation (Rs/ha)</p> <p>Design Points:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Above Surface ○ Below Surface <p>985.04 1771.66</p> <p>X1 = A X2 = B</p>